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EVENT TOURISM IN HISTORICAL AND CULTURAL COMPLEXES (THE EXAMPLE OF ORGANIZING THE 130TH ANNIVERSARY OF S. A. ESENIN AT THE KONSTANTINOVO MUSEUM)

Abstract. The article examines the specifics of the development of event tourism based on historical and cultural complexes, in particular, by the example of the organization of the All-Russian Poetry Festival dedicated to the 130th anniversary of the birth of S. A. Yesenin, held at the State Museum-Reserve of S. A. Yesenin in the village of Konstantinovo, Ryazan region; the study focuses on the role of such events in shaping the tourist image to enhance the cultural space of the region and increase the tourist attractiveness of the territory with significant historical and cultural potential. Special attention is paid to the analysis of organizational aspects and difficulties encountered in holding mass events in territories where the historical environment requires a special mode of operation and preservation of authenticity. The work also analyzes the media perception of the holiday, identifies the causes of public discontent reflected in social networks and regional media, and makes recommendations for improving the practice of holding such events in the future. The methodological basis of the research consists of systematic, cultural and event-communicative approaches, the scientific novelty of the research lies in the comprehensive assessment of event tourism as a tool of cultural policy and territorial branding, where the emphasis is not only on tourism, but also on the socio-communicative dimension.

Keywords: event tourism, museum-reserve, cultural heritage, organization of holidays, S. A. Yesenin, Konstantinovo, image of the region

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СОБЫТИЙНЫЙ ТУРИЗМ В ИСТОРИКО-КУЛЬТУРНЫХ КОМПЛЕКСАХ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ПРАЗДНИКА 130-ЛЕТИЯ С. А. ЕСЕНИНА В МУЗЕЕ СЕЛА КОНСТАНТИНОВО)

В статье рассматриваются особенности развития событийного туризма на базе историко-культурных комплексов, в частности на примере организации Всероссийского праздника поэзии, посвященного 130-летию со дня рождения С. А. Есенина, прошедшего в Государственном музее-заповеднике С. А. Есенина в селе Константиново Рязанской области; исследование акцентирует внимание на роли подобных мероприятий в формировании туристического имиджа региона, активизации культурного пространства и повышении туристской привлекательности территории, обладающей значительным историко-культурным потенциалом. Особое внимание уделяется анализу организационных аспектов и возникающих трудностей при проведении массовых событий на территориях, где историческая среда требует особого режима эксплуатации и сохранения аутентичности, в работе также анализируется медийное восприятие праздника, выявляются причины общественного недовольства, отраженного в социальных сетях и региональных СМИ, и формулируются рекомендации по совершенствованию практики проведения подобных мероприятий в будущем. Методологическую основу исследования составляют системный, культурологический и событийно-коммуникативный подходы, научная новизна исследования заключается в комплексной оценке событийного туризма как инструмента культурной политики и территориального брендинга, где акцент делается не только на туристическом, но и на социально-коммуникационном измерении.

Ключевые слова: *событийный туризм, музей-заповедник, культурное наследие, организация праздников, С. А. Есенин, Константиново, имидж региона*

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Introduction

Contemporary forms of cultural tourism, among which event tourism occupies a special place, are becoming increasingly important in the context of regional development, the formation of cultural identity, and the promotion of historical and cultural heritage. Based on this, the relevance of the study is determined by the growing role of event practices in the cultural policy of Russian regions, as well as the need to find effective models for organizing large cultural events in historical and protected areas.

The scientific problem of the study is to identify the contradiction between the high cultural potential of historical and cultural complexes and the insufficient degree of organizational and infrastructural readiness to receive mass tourist flows.

The aim of the study is to analyze the features and problems of organizing event tourism in historical and cultural complexes using the example of the celebration of the 130th anniversary of S. A. Yesenin in the village of Konstantinovo. To achieve this goal, methods of systemic and cultural analysis were used, as well as empirical methods – content analysis of media and social network publications, observation and comparative analysis of event management practices. The methodological basis of the article is based on the works of Russian researchers in the field of cultural tourism and regional branding (A. V. Firsova, V. S. Firsov, T. V. Kovalchuk, G. M. Dekhtyar, A. I. Minazetdinova), which allows us to consider the event not only as a cultural phenomenon, but also as a socio-communicative phenomenon.

Event tourism as a tool for developing the cultural space of the region

It should be noted that event tourism as an independent area of tourist activity is a complex socio-cultural and economic phenomenon that integrates elements of cultural, recreational, and educational tourism, while its essence lies in the organization and attendance by tourists of events specially timed to coincide with certain dates, themes, or traditions of public, historical, or cultural significance, which emphasizes its interdisciplinary nature and high potential for the formation

of unique tourism products. Thus, according to the definition proposed by N. F. Lazitskaya, Z. Z. Ekimova, and A. M. Khakhalina, event tourism should be considered as “a type of tourism associated with tourists visiting the venue of an event, different from their permanent place of residence, at a specific time corresponding to the dates of the event” [5, pp. 85–94]. Thus, the key feature of this type of tourist activity is the temporary nature of the event, which gives it the character of an exclusive and, therefore, economically and culturally attractive product that motivates people to travel.

At the current stage of development of the hospitality industry, event tourism is considered by researchers to be one of the most dynamically developing segments of the tourism market, performing not only entertainment, but also important communicative, educational, and image-forming functions. For example, K. A. Tolstoguzova emphasizes that event tourism is “a promising and actively growing area of tourism that can significantly influence the development of the socio-economic situation in the regions,” since the organization of large events stimulates the development of infrastructure, creates new jobs, increases the investment attractiveness of territories, and contributes to the formation of sustainable regional brands [11, p. 5]. Consequently, the significance of event tourism for the organization of tourism services lies in its ability to serve as a catalyst for the spatial and economic development of destinations, giving them additional tourist value and competitive advantages.

According to research by N. F. Lazitskaya and co-authors, event tourism has a positive impact on the development of tourist areas, as it contributes to an increase in tourist flow, longer stays, diversification of tourist offerings, occupancy of accommodation facilities and catering establishments, and encourages repeat visits [5, p. 88]. In addition, one of the significant features of event tourism is its multiplier effect, which is reflected in the rapid development of related industries – transportation, trade, services, souvenir production, and small business. This effect makes events

not only a tool for promoting the region, but also a sustainable factor in its socio-economic revitalization.

Researchers note that event tourism is capable of mitigating the problem of seasonality, typical for many tourist destinations, by organizing events in the “low” and off-season periods, which ensures a more even distribution of tourist flows and increases the utilization of accommodation facilities and infrastructure [5, p. 90]. This opportunity makes event tourism a tool for strategic planning and an effective means of managing tourist flows at the regional level.

E. M. Kokoeva, A. D. Ivanov, M. O. Rumyantsev, and E. M. Shevchenko point out that the development of event tourism in Russia is based on rich cultural and historical resources and diverse forms of regional identity, and therefore the potential for holding events in domestic regions is extremely high. According to the researchers, holding festivals, holidays, reenactments, and exhibitions is becoming an important factor in increasing the attractiveness of destinations, creating sustainable communication links between cultural heritage and tourist demand [4, pp. 114–118].

In this context, event tourism is not only a form of leisure, but also a tool for preserving and promoting cultural traditions, which gives it strategic importance for state tourism policy.

Researchers pay particular attention to the institutionalization of event tourism in Russia: G. M. Dekhtyar and A. I. Minazetdinova point out that the current policy of state authorities is aimed at forming a systematic approach to the development of event tourism, which is reflected in the “Strategy for the Development of Tourism in the Russian Federation until 2035,” where the priority tasks include modernizing the national calendar of events, updating event tourism programs, and the mandatory holding of mass events at various levels aimed at attracting tourists to the country’s regions [2, p. 16], thereby creating the conditions for strengthening event tourism as one of the key areas of state policy in the field of tourism and cultural development of territories.

A. V. Glotko and A. Yu. Shchukina, analyzing the problems and prospects of event tourism, emphasize that the successful development of this direction requires not only organizational efforts, but also the presence of a conceptual cultural basis that ensures the semantic integrity of the event, its symbolic connection with local identity and historical context, which contributes to the formation of a positive image of the region and sustained interest on the part of tourists [1, pp. 125–128].

Thus, analysis of scientific sources allows us to conclude that event tourism, with its pronounced social and cultural orientation, plays a key role in the organization of tourism services, acting as an integrator of economic, cultural, and communication processes, in particular, it stimulates the development of destinations, contributes to the formation of a positive image of the territory, ensures the growth of tourist activity and the diversification of tourist products, and creates opportunities for synergy between the spheres of culture, tourism, and regional development. The combination of these factors allows event tourism to be viewed as a strategic resource capable of transforming local initiatives into sustainable forms of cultural and tourist activity, thereby ensuring the long-term development of territories.

Historical and cultural complexes, which include estate ensembles and museum-reserves, have become significant spaces for realizing the potential of event tourism in recent decades, as they possess a unique combination of spatial scale, cultural richness, and natural landscape surroundings, creating conditions for organizing events of various formats – from chamber festivals to large-scale celebrations with audiences of thousands. As O. Yu. Nelzina, museum-reserves and estate complexes “are venues directly related to the themes of museums and attract visitors with unique concepts, within which thematic events held in various formats, as well as the organization of specialized tours, contribute to the popularization of museum activities, the formation of the region’s image, and the development of territories” [6]. It is in this context that estate complexes become

unique cultural and leisure centers, where the synthesis of cultural, educational, and recreational elements contributes to the formation of a multi-level tourist experience for visitors.

As shown by E. V. Seredina's research, museum territories have significant potential for creating a comfortable environment that meets the needs of mass visitors, while preserving the historical landscape and natural surroundings becomes an essential condition for the sustainable development of such spaces [9, pp. 151–166]. The large open areas of museum-reserves – park areas, glades, inner courtyards of estates, natural coastlines – allow not only for large-scale celebrations to be held, but also for the formation of a multi-level event infrastructure, including concert venues, fairgrounds, craft workshops, food outlets, and souvenir shops, making tourists' stay not only culturally rich but also comfortable in terms of everyday life.

At the same time, as T. V. Kovalchuk emphasizes, when organizing events in museum complexes, it is important to preserve authenticity and ethnographic character, ensure the correct use of museum objects, and take into account the characteristics of the landscape and exhibition environment [3, pp. 259–263]: Thus, the experience of the Kizhi Museum-Reserve shows that developing a calendar of events that correspond to the museum's theme and the spirit of the territory not only stimulates visitors' interest but also contributes to the involvement of the local community in the preservation and interpretation of cultural heritage.

Thematic folk craft festivals, ethnographic fairs, and theatrical reenactments of traditional rituals and holidays create a special atmosphere of "participation" in history and culture, in which each participant becomes not just an observer, but a participant in cultural action.

In her research, E. L. Russkikh draws attention to the fact that events based on local myths and cultural archetypes can transform museum space into a space of participation, where visitors' emotional involvement is formed and the cultural identity of the territory is strengthened [8, pp. 26–29]. Thus, the example of the Idnakar Museum-Reserve,

which uses the theme of heroes in its interactive programs, demonstrates that historical and cultural complexes can form unique scenarios for event tourism, combining educational, playful, and entertaining forms of cultural interaction.

As M. V. Skorokhodov rightly points out, museum-reserves and estate complexes not only perform the function of protecting cultural heritage, but also become significant centers of regional development, as their activities contribute to the creation of jobs not only in the museums themselves, but also in related areas of tourism and hospitality, making them important elements of the region's tourism infrastructure [10, pp. 304–312]. In this sense, event tourism, implemented because of estate complexes, acts as an economic and cultural catalyst, bringing together various forms of creative, educational, and entrepreneurial activity.

A striking example of the successful integration of the event format into the museum environment is the activity of the Murano Estate Museum-Reserve, described by E. V. Shaparina. As the researcher notes, modern museums, while preserving their traditional functions, are increasingly turning to various genres of museum activity, creating a lively atmosphere of communication and participation [13, pp. 119–125]: for example, Murano has developed and implemented programs such as "Haymaking in Murano", "Maslenitsa", "Jam Day," "Winter Holidays", and theatrical tours of the "Manor Kitchen", which transform the museum space into a platform for emotional and interactive engagement with cultural heritage. Such holidays combine excursion, entertainment, and gastronomic components, helping to attract a wide range of people and develop tourist traffic: during the Maslenitsa celebrations alone, more than 5,500 people visited the museum, which demonstrates the significant potential of such events.

As noted by A. V. and V. S. Firsov, contemporary trends in museum design are aimed at developing new technologies for interacting with visitors and developing partnerships with local communities [12, pp. 36–42]. Modern museums are becoming initiators of art

residencies, cultural festivals, educational laboratories, art mediation, and routes in the natural and cultural landscape. This approach allows historical and cultural complexes to become active centers of cultural life in the region, where event practices serve as a tool not only for promoting the museum, but also for involving residents in the development of local tourism industries.

Thus, manor and museum-reserve complexes are optimal venues for event tourism, as they offer unique conditions for the synthesis of cultural, natural, and recreational potential. Their spatial organization allows for the combination of large-scale mass events—concerts, theatrical performances, craft fairs, gastronomic festivals – with traditional museum practices, including excursions, exhibitions, and lectures, making such spaces a universal cultural and tourist platform capable of ensuring both the preservation of historical heritage and the sustainable development of the region.

The S. A. Yesenin State Museum-Reserve as a venue for event tourism

The S. A. Yesenin State Museum-Reserve, located in the village of Konstantinovo in the Rybnovsky District of the Ryazan Region, is a unique historical and cultural complex with significant potential for the development of event tourism, as it combines memorial, natural landscape, and educational functions, acting not only as the guardian of national poetic memory, but also as a modern platform for cultural interaction. Founded on October 2, 1965, the museum was the result of a long process of public and state reflection on the significance of S. A. Yesenin's creative legacy: as early as 1926, the first meeting to perpetuate the memory of the poet was held in Moscow, at which it was proposed to create a reading room named after Yesenin in his native village; in 1955, an exhibition entitled "The Life and Work of Yesenin" was organized in the poet's parental home, which had previously housed the village library; In 1984, in accordance with a resolution of the Council of Ministers of the RSFSR, the S. A. Yesenin State Museum-Reserve was created, which included not only sites in Konstantinovo, but also memorable places in the town of Spas-Klepiki.

Today, the total area of the museum-reserve is 22.13 hectares, which speaks to the scale and landscape integrity of the museum space. The complex includes key memorial sites directly related to the poet's life and work: his parents' estate, the Church of the Kazan Icon of the Mother of God, the Chapel of the Holy Spirit, the restored zemstvo school (in 1995, on the centenary of Yesenin's birth), the house of L. I. Kashina, now the museum of the poem "Anna Snegina", as well as the Spas-Klepikovskaya second-class teacher training school. Currently, the museum has seven main exhibitions reflecting various stages of Yesenin's life and work. As a result of ongoing reconstruction and restoration, the museum space continues to expand actively: for example, for the poet's 125th anniversary in 2020, the carriage yard, barn, bathhouse, and greenhouse were restored based on archival photographs, which significantly enhanced the effect of historical accuracy and authenticity of perception.

As noted by E. V. Seredina, such museum-reserves, with their large territory and rich architectural and landscape potential, represent "cultural heritage organisms" where it is possible to harmoniously combine the preservation of the historical environment with the implementation of modern event formats aimed at engaging a wide audience [9, p. 152]. Therefore, the S. A. Yesenin State Museum-Reserve is a striking example of such integration: every year, festivals, exhibitions, plein air events, fairs, and literary celebrations are held on its vast territory, turning Konstantinovo into a center of attraction for tourists, researchers, and lovers of Russian poetry.

Organization of the celebration of the 130th anniversary of S. A. Yesenin: a cultural event and tourist project

The celebration of the 130th anniversary of Sergei Yesenin's birth, which took place in October 2025, occupies a special place among the museum's events. The scale and multi-level nature of this event allow it to be viewed as an indicator of effective interaction between cultural, administrative, and public structures, as well as an example of modern cultural management. The anniversary celebrations were organized by the Government

of the Ryazan Region, the regional Ministry of Culture, the S. A. Yesenin State Museum-Reserve, the Ryazan Regional Universal Scientific Library named after Gorky, the Ryazan Historical and Architectural Museum-Reserve, and the ANO Center for Contemporary Culture. Funding was provided by the regional and federal budgets, as well as by sponsors: the general partner was PJSC Rosneft, and the technical partner was PJSC Rostelecom. The book publisher Eksmo, the companies Relief-Center LLC and Gamma JSC, Gazprom Transgaz Moscow LLC, and the construction company Green Garden – Our Home Group also participated.

From October 3 to 5, 2025, Ryazan and the village of Konstantinovo became the centers of celebration, which included three major festivals: “Yesenin in the City”, “Yesenin. Out of Time”, and “Konstantinov Childhood”. On October 3, the city festival “Yesenin in the City” was held in Ryazan, which included a poetry rally, an open microphone, theatrical performances, a youth festival, an exhibition “The Poet in Each of Us”, and concert programs. On October 4, the village of Konstantinovo hosted the All-Russian Poetry Festival, which lasted from 12:00 to 20:00 and included the festival “Yesenin. Beyond Time”. Honored Artist of Russia Ekaterina Guseva hosted the festival, and the central events of the day were the one-man show “Hooligan. Confession” performed by People’s Artist of Russia Sergei Bezrukov, the street performance “My Yesenin” by Vlad Malenko, the musical and poetic program “Poetry as Poetry” with the participation of Anton Shagin, Alexei Vertkov, Pavel Tabakov, Ksenia Kutepova, and Dmitry Dyuzhev, as well as the closing concert by the group Pelageya. Special attention was paid to poetry battles featuring teams of popular artists Alexei Kravchenko and Valeria Lanskaya, a craft fair and festive trade – the traditional Konstantinovskaya Fair, where guests could purchase folk crafts and regional products. The celebrations ended with the laying of flowers at the poet’s monument in his parents’ estate and the reading of poems in different languages, including Arabic.

On October 5, Konstantinov hosted the Konstantinov Childhood art festival, aimed

at young audiences and family leisure, where guests could participate in immersive performances, master classes, plein air painting, poetry mazes, and traditional games, as noted by O. Yu. Nelzina, “event practices implemented on the basis of museum-reserves contribute not only to the popularization of museum activities, but also to the formation of regional identity and the strengthening of the image of the territory in the cultural space of the country” [6]. The celebration of the 130th anniversary of S. A. Yesenin in the village of Konstantinovo can be seen as an example of this concept in action: the museum-reserve has become not only the keeper of poetic heritage, but also an active participant in creating a modern cultural space where tradition blends naturally with new forms of public interaction.

Problems of organizing and perceiving the event: media reflection and public response

Despite extensive preparations and significant organizational efforts on the part of regional authorities and cultural institutions, the celebration of the 130th anniversary of Sergei Alexandrovich Yesenin’s birth, which took place on October 4–5, 2025, at the S. A. Yesenin State Museum-Reserve in the village of Konstantinovo, began with a negative reaction from a significant portion of visitors and caused a wide public outcry, forming a purely negative media image of the event: already in the first hours of the celebrations, numerous comments from Ryazan residents and guests from other regions began to appear on social networks and in local media, expressing their outrage at the level of organization of the event, which is typical for situations when the expectation of a cultural holiday as an event of high symbolic significance contradicts the everyday aspects of its implementation, leading to cognitive dissonance between the image and the experience of the event.

Expectations for the festival were indeed extremely high: virtually all regional news portals and cultural platforms wrote about the upcoming events, announcements of festivals, concerts, exhibitions were actively distributed on social media, and the event itself was positioned as the central cultural event of

the year in the Ryazan region. However, as the audience's reaction showed, the reality fell far short of expectations – on the day of the main celebrations, October 4, the information space was filled with reports of numerous organizational problems.

The transport situation was perceived most acutely: according to official announcements, the transfer from Ryazan to Konstantinovo was to be provided by a sufficient number of free buses, but in practice, thousands of people wishing to attend the festival were faced with chaotic logistics and a shortage of transport: instead of spacious buses, small minibuses designed to carry only 20 people were provided (transport ran on a schedule, one minibus per hour), which meant that people waited for hours for departure, crowded in queues, and often returned without ever reaching the venue. As reported by the regional publication RG62.info, “citizens filmed videos at bus stops and posted them on social media, calling what was happening ‘mocking people’¹.

Similar reports were published by other regional media outlets: for example, the portal 62info.ru noted that “Ryazan residents were struck by the huge queues for buses from Konstantinovo², and a message appeared on the Zen platform under the headline “Ryazan residents cannot get to Konstantinovo for the celebration of Sergei Yesenin’s 130th birthday”, which emphasized that “the transport situation was critical, people stood in line for over an hour, and many were late for the start of the main events”³. Such posts were accompanied by videos and photos illustrating miles-long traffic jams and crowded bus stops.

The situation in Konstantinovo itself also caused numerous complaints: according to the publication Komsomolskaya Pravda – Ryazan, about 18,000 people arrived in the village, but only one stationary toilet was working, and the additional portable toilets stopped functioning by lunchtime. Queues for sanitary facilities reached an hour's wait, which became one of the central topics of discussion on social media. There were also reports of long queues at food outlets, water shortages, and a lack of sufficient garbage containers, which led to temporary domestic difficulties and a deterioration in the sanitary condition of the area⁴.

The situation with access to museum facilities caused particular dissatisfaction: despite the fact that the organizers had previously announced free admission on the day of the holiday, visitors were required to purchase tickets on site, which was perceived as a breach of promises and reinforced the negative perception of the event. Technical problems, such as poor sound quality, poor stage placement, and limited visibility, were also noted in numerous publications and comments. The portal 62info.ru quoted visitors who wrote: “You can't hear anything from the stage, and if you're not standing in the front rows, you can't see anything either. Everything is blocked, people are standing on the hills, but even there the sound is delayed”⁵.

Transportation problems only worsened after the celebrations ended: as reported in the “Typical Ryazan” community on the VKontakte platform, “Ryazan residents could not leave Konstantinovo after Yesenin's anniversary – there was very little of the promised free transportation, and taxis were charging triple

- 1 Residents and visitors to Ryazan have described the transport arrangements in Konstantinovo as a mockery [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://rg62.info/2025/10/05/zhiteli-i-gosti-ryazani-nazvali-izdevatelstvom-organizacziyu-transporta-v-konstantinovo-video/> (date of access: 06.10.2025).
- 2 Ryazantsev was struck by the huge queues for buses from Konstantinovo [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://62info.ru/news/obshchestvo/141466-ryazantsev-porazili-ogromnye-ocheredi-v-avtobusy-iz-konstantinova/> (date of access: 06.10.2025).
- 3 Ryazan residents cannot get to Konstantinovo to celebrate the 130th anniversary of Sergei Yesenin [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://dzen.ru/a/aOEWIKNCZnqRd61P> (date of access: 06.10.2025).
- 4 Traffic jam from Rybný and a queue for the toilet. Several thousand people came to the Yesenin festival in Konstantinovo [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://www.ryazan.kp.ru/online/news/6603977/> (date of access: 06.10.2025).
- 5 Ryazantsev was struck by the huge queues for buses from Konstantinovo [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://62info.ru/news/obshchestvo/141466-ryazantsev-porazili-ogromnye-ocheredi-v-avtobusy-iz-konstantinova/> (date of access: 06.10.2025).

the usual price”¹, More than 2,500 cars arriving for the festival caused kilometer-long traffic jams, and, as eyewitnesses noted, “it was impossible to leave after Pelageya’s concert – cars stood motionless for hours”².

Some visitors were annoyed not only by the lack of adequate comfort conditions, but also by the behavior of certain museum staff members who, according to eyewitness accounts, were overly harsh and unwilling to engage in dialogue with the large crowds: social media repeatedly noted that some museum employees rushed visitors during their tour of the exhibits, urging them to leave the halls quickly, which created a feeling of a formal attitude towards guests and disrupted the solemn atmosphere. In addition, despite the scale of the anniversary events, many participants described the cultural program as monotonous and insufficiently dynamic, noting the “general dullness” of the events and the lack of interactive forms of audience engagement³. These observations confirm the importance of not only organizational and technical training, but also communication and psychological training for museum staff, since the perception of any event is largely determined by the emotional tone of communication between employees and visitors.

Thus, despite the presence of leading Russian artists in the festive program – Sergei Bezrukov, Sergei Nikonenk, Pelageya, Anton Shagin, Dmitry Dyuzhev, and others – the emotional impression of the performances was offset by the general organizational chaos. On social media and in regional media, active discussion of the event’s problems continued for several days after the celebrations, resulting in a sustained negative media discourse around the anniversary, which undermines the reputational potential of the cultural event, turning it from a means of promoting the region into a source of public irritation.

This situation clearly demonstrates that even with significant financial and administrative resources, as well as the involvement of well-known cultural figures, the success

of an event project in historical and cultural complexes depends on a systematic approach to logistics, infrastructure, and communication with the audience, since the discrepancy between expectations and the actual conditions of the events becomes a factor that determines not only public opinion but also the image of the region as a tourist destination.

Ways to improve the organization of event tourism in historical and cultural complexes

To minimize reputational risks and reduce the likelihood of a recurrence of the organizational failures described above when holding mass events in historical and cultural complexes, it is advisable to develop a multi-level strategy for the preparation and implementation of events, in which integrated planning of transport logistics, sanitary and technical support, and communication policy is considered not as an auxiliary part of the scenario, but as a basic part, since it is precisely the mismatch between the domestic infrastructure and the expectations of the audience that quickly transforms into viral negativity on social networks and limits the positive image effect of even the most highly professional artistic programs.

First, at the event design stage, it is necessary to conduct a detailed transport model with a calculation of the capacity of the main approaches, parking lots, and route corridors, taking into account the expected peak times (entry/exit peaks, concert breaks, etc.), as well as conclude partnership agreements with major carriers and the municipality for the provision of large shuttle buses and organized parking areas, providing for alternative schemes (container parking with transfer, dedicated evacuation corridors), – an approach that is consistent with the ideas of systematic flow management and prevents scenarios where thousands of people find themselves “stuck” in narrow entrances and crowded minibuses, which in modern conditions is immediately translated into negative content in the media space.

1 Ryazan residents were unable to travel to Konstantinovo for Yesenin’s anniversary. There was no transportation [Electronic resource]. URL: https://vk.com/wall-121930396_149278 (date of access: 06.10.2025).

2 Ibid.

3 Typical Ryazan. Impressions from the holiday in Konstantinovo [Electronic resource]. URL: https://vk.com/tr_ryazan?from=groups&w=wall-33504019_2739247 (date of access: 06.10.2025).

Secondly, planning for sanitary, hygienic, and gastronomic infrastructure should be based on standards for calculating sanitary facilities and food outlets per visitor, include a system for monitoring the performance of dry toilets and reserving contractors for replacement/maintenance, and provide for zoning of queues with protection from wind/precipitation and the temporary placement of additional mobile sanitary facilities during peak periods, since the lack of a sufficient number of functioning toilets and adequate catering services is a factor that generates consistently negative reviews and increases social discontent, as empirical cases of Russian museum festivals show.

Thirdly, ticketing and admission policies must be carefully thought out: if free admission is announced, this is a commitment that must be monitored using digital tools (electronic registration, limited time slots, QR control at the entrance), and if ticketing is planned, a transparent tariff grid, priority channels for privileged categories, and separate flows for excursions are necessary to avoid conflicts on site and reduce tension among visitors, while optimizing flows and the predictability of the load on the museum infrastructure.

Fourth, the regulation of stage and technical aspects (sound, lighting, video broadcasting, stage and grandstand placement taking into account the terrain) must be accompanied by mandatory testing during rehearsals in field conditions and the organization of feedback points – volunteer and information centers – because even a program of high artistic quality loses its impact with poor sound or limited visibility, which is then instantly discussed on social media and undermines trust in the organizers.

Fifth, an effective communication strategy with the target audience and media partners, based on the principles of transparency and anticipation of problems, obliges the organizers to inform in advance about possible inconveniences and measures to minimize them (clear instructions for transfers, alternative routes, free shuttle schedules, recommendations on arrival times), prepare PR messages and an operational crisis communication plan with the appointment of persons

responsible for responding on social media and handling complaints – because in the digital media sphere, it is the speed and quality of the organizers' response to negativity that determines the further tone of the discourse and the event's ability to restore its reputation, which corresponds to the provision on the importance of the image component of event tourism and the need for well-thought-out media support, as stated in studies on state and regional policy in the field of event tourism.

Sixth, the involvement of local communities and the formation of partnerships with local businesses and non-profit organizations at the design and implementation stage – from providing food outlets and market stalls to organizing volunteer teams and parking services – not only enhances the economic impact of the event and distributes the load, but also increases the degree of local involvement and willingness of residents to assist in solving operational logistics tasks.

Seventh, the introduction of digital management tools – mobile applications with a map of the venue, real-time schedule, transport and queue status, a notification system, and the ability to leave feedback, as well as monitoring social media using sentiment analysis and rapid moderation systems – not only improves the user experience during the event, but also allows for quick response to incidents and online adjustment of operational decisions, mitigating potential negativity in the media space.

Finally, a mandatory element is post-event analysis involving independent experts, volunteers, and representatives of visitor groups – conducting satisfaction surveys, auditing logistics and infrastructure, detailed analysis of incidents, and publication of a report with conclusions and a plan of corrective measures, since openness to criticism and demonstration of steps to correct mistakes are key tools for restoring audience trust and the reputation of a cultural event, which logically follows from research on image issues and the prospects for event tourism.

Summarizing the above in practical recommendations, it can be argued that preventing reputational damage when organizing

large events in historical and cultural complexes requires a comprehensive approach, in which preventive planning of logistics and infrastructure, transparent and proactive communication, active involvement of the local community, and the use of digital monitoring and management tools form a unified field of organizational practices capable of transforming cultural festivals into successful image projects rather than sources of prolonged public discontent, as evidenced by both analytical calculations on the development of event tourism in the Russian Federation and empirical cases of museum celebrations.

Let us consider these recommendations using a table.

Conclusion

The study allows us to conclude that the successful organization of event tourism in historical and cultural complexes requires

a comprehensive approach that combines cultural mission, tourism potential, and modern technologies for managing mass events: the example of the celebration of the 130th anniversary of S. A. Yesenin in the village of Konstantinovo clearly demonstrates that even with a high level of cultural and artistic content of the event, insufficiently developed logistics, infrastructure, and communication strategy can cause significant reputational damage and distort the public's perception of the holiday. As we know, in the digital media reality, every organizational oversight is instantly broadcast on social networks, creating a negative information background, which requires organizers to have not only cultural but also media competence.

Thus, event tourism in historical and cultural complexes should be viewed as a multi-component process that includes flow

Table 1. Recommendations aimed at improving the quality of event organization in historical and cultural complexes

	Recommendation	Objective
1	Development of a detailed transport model with capacity calculations, involvement of major carriers, and organization of parking and shuttle services.	To avoid traffic congestion and ensure comfortable access for visitors.
2	Planning of sanitary and gastronomic infrastructure with reserve capacity, standards, and monitoring of toilets and food outlets.	To prevent inconvenience and negative feedback on social media.
3	Development of a transparent ticketing and admission policy with electronic control, registration, and clear access rules.	Reduce conflict situations and ensure an even flow of visitors.
4	Optimization of the stage and technical aspects: testing sound, lighting, grandstand layout, creation of information centers and volunteer posts.	Improve the quality of the program's perception and reduce technical risks.
5	Developing a communication strategy: informing people in advance about inconveniences, providing a crisis plan for PR communications and responding to negativity on social media.	Maintain a positive image of the event and prevent the spread of negative reviews.
6	Involving local communities and partnerships with local businesses, creating volunteer teams, and distributing the infrastructure load.	Strengthen local involvement and distribute responsibility for the organization.
7	Introduction of digital tools: mobile applications, online maps, social media analytics, real-time moderation, and feedback.	Improve the manageability of the event and respond quickly to emerging problems.
8	Insufficient training of museum staff to work with large audiences	Conduct professional training for museum staff focused on the principles of service culture.
9	Lack of interactive forms of visitor participation	Update interactive museum technologies, which will contribute to strengthening the emotional involvement of the public.

management, audience interaction, support for a comfortable environment, and the formation of a sustainable positive image of the territory. The implementation of these

principles will make such events not one-off promotions, but long-term tools for the cultural and tourist development of Russia's regions.

References

1. Glotko, A. V., Shchukina, A. Yu. (2022). *Problemy i perspektivy razvitiya sobyitiynogo turizma v Rossiyskoy Federatsii [Problems and prospects of event tourism development in the Russian Federation]*. Problemy i perspektivy razvitiya turizma v Rossiyskoy Federatsii [Problems and prospects of tourism development in the Russian Federation]: Proceedings of VII Russian conference with international participants. Simferopol: V. I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University, 125–128. (In Russ.).
2. Dekhtyar, G. M., Minazetdinova, A. I. (2023). *Sovremennoe sostoyanie i perspektivy razvitiya sobyitiynogo turizma v Rossii [The current state and prospects of development of event tourism in Russia]*. *Voprosy otraslevoy ekonomiki [Questions of the branch economy]*, 1 (1), 15–19. (In Russ.).
3. Kovalchuk, T. V. (2016). *Opyt organizatsii sobyitiynykh meropriyatiy v muzee-zapovednike «Kizhi» [Experience of organizing event activities in the «Kizhi» museum-reserve]*. *Razvitie fizicheskoy kultury, sporta i turizma: opyt regionov [Development of physical culture, sports and tourism: the regional experience]*: Proceedings of the conference of the Institute of Physical Culture, Sports and Tourism of Petrozavodsk State University. Petrozavodsk: Petrozavodsk State University, Pp. 259–263. (In Russ.).
4. Kokoeva, E. M., Ivanov, A. D., & Rumyantsev, M. O., et al. (2023). *Osobennosti razvitiya sobyitiynogo turizma: faktory, resursy, spetsifika [Features of event tourism development: factors, resources, specifics]*. *Turizm i industriya gostepriimstva: sovremennoe sostoyanie i tendentsii razvitiya [Tourism and hospitality industry: current status and development trends]*: Proceedings of V international scientific and practical conference. Rostov-on-Don: LLC «DGTU-PRINT», 114–118. (In Russ.).
5. Lazitskaya, N. F., Yekimova, Z. Z., & Khakhalina, A. M. (2022). *Tendentsii razvitiya sobyitiynogo turizma v mire i Rossiyskoy Federatsii [Trends in the development of event tourism in the world and the Russian Federation]*. *Uchenye zapiski Krymskogo federal'nogo universiteta imeni V. I. Vernadskogo. Geografiya. Geologiya [Scientific Notes of the V. I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University. Geography. Geology]*, 8(3), 85–94. (In Russ.).
6. Nelzina, O. Yu. (2022). *Muzeyi-zapovedniki i usadebnye komplekсы kak ploshchadki dlya provedeniya sobyitiynykh meropriyatiy [Museums-reserves and estate complexes as venues for event activities]*. *Kulturologicheskiy zhurnal [Cultural journal]*, 1(47). DOI 10.34685/HI.2022.41.12.006. (In Russ.).
7. Pecheritsyna, V. Yu., Tolstykh, O. N. (2020). *Perspektivy razvitiya sobyitiynogo turizma v Rossiyskoy Federatsii [Prospects for event tourism development in the Russian Federation]*. *Tendentsii i problemy razvitiya industriya turizma i gostepriimstva [Trends and challenges of developing tourism and hospitality industry]*: Proceedings of VII Interregional scientific and practical conference dedicated to the 105 anniversaries of Ryazan State University named after S. A. Yesenin. Ryazan: Ryazan State University named after S. A. Yesenin, 5–61. (In Russ.).
8. Russkikh, E. L. (2022). *Bogatyrskaya tematika v deyatel'nosti muzeya-zapovednika «Ildnakar» kak osnova dlya formirovaniya prostranstva souchastiya [Heroic themes in the activities of the museum «Ildnakar» as a basis for the formation of a space of participation]*. *Vestnik Muzeya arkheologii i etnografii Permskogo Predural'ya [Bulletin of the Museum of Archeology and Ethnography of the Perm Urals]*, 12, 26–29. (In Russ.).
9. Seredina, E. V. (2020). *Muzeyi-zapovedniki kak obyekt turistskogo palomnichestva [Museums-reserves as an object of tourist pilgrimage]*. In: *Turizm i muzeyi: sinergeticheskiy effekt vzaimodeystviya [Tourism and museums: the synergistic effect of interaction]*. Moscow: Publishing house «Znanie-M», 151–166. (In Russ.).
10. Skorokhodov, M. V. (2021). *Razvitie muzeev-zapovednikov i muzeev-usadeb kak put' kulturnogo vrozhdeniya russkoy provincii [Development of museums-reserves and estate museums as a way of cultural revival of the Russian province]*. In: *Antsiferovskiy sbornik [The Antsiferian Collection]*. Vol. II. Moscow-Berlin: LLC «Direkt-Media», 304–312. (In Russ.).

11. Tolstoguzova, K. A. (2017). Rol' sobytiynogo turizma v razvitii strany [The role of event tourism in the development of the country]. *Chelovecheskij progress [Human Progress]*, 3(11), 5–9. (In Russ.).
12. Firsova, A. V., Firsov, V. S. (2024). Muzeynye tekhnologii, napravlennye na turistskoe razvitie territorii [Museum technologies aimed at tourist development of the territory]. *Geografiya i turizm [Geography and tourism]*, 2 (14), 36–42. (In Russ.).
13. Shaparina, E. V. (2015). Sovremennaya zhizn' muzeya. Programmy i prazdniki v usad'be «Murano-vo» [Modern life of the museum. Programmes and festivals in the Memorial Estate «Mouranovo»]. *Sovremennye problemy servisa i turizma [Service and Tourism: Current Challenges]*, 9(2), 119–125. (In Russ.).